

Histomorphology of the Muscle Tissue System (Literature Analysis)

Rashidov Khujakhan Karim son, Erboboyev Umarjon Ikram son

Samarkand State Veterinary Medicine, University of Livestock and Biotechnology, Talented students

Elmurad Abdigulomovich Mukhtarov

V.F.F.D., (PhD) assistant, Samarkand State Veterinary Medicine, University of Livestock and Biotechnology

Mizayev Ziyer Rajabovich

Assistant, Samarkand State Veterinary Medicine, University of Livestock and Biotechnology

Nomuradova Zuhra Faizulaevna, Ph.D.

Assistant Professor, Samarkand State Veterinary Medicine, University of Livestock and Biotechnology

Abstract: Muscle tissue consists of cells specialized for contraction. Muscles are divided into three types according to their structure and function: skeletal muscle cells, cardiac muscle cells, and smooth muscle cells. Skeletal and cardiac muscle cells are called striated muscle cells because they display alternating rows of striations. In all types of muscles, contraction occurs as a result of the movement of myosin and actin enzymes. Nuclei of muscle cell and muscle fiber are synonymous. Knowing this, we will analyze the literature together.

Keywords: Smooth muscle, transverse muscle, cardiac muscle. Myofilament, myoprotofibril, myofibril, actin, myosin. Smooth myocyte

Enter. Muscle tissues are specialized for contraction, and their cells or fibers are characterized by the presence of special threads (myofilaments, myoprotofibrils). These filaments consist of molecules of actin and myosin proteins, which have a fibrous structure. More complex contractile structures - myofibrils - are formed from these threads.

There are smooth and transverse muscles in the body of animals. Cross-extensive muscles are divided into skeletal and cardiac muscles, and cardiac muscle, in turn, is divided into working (contracting) and conducting muscle fibers. Also, during embryonic development, smooth muscles develop from mesenchyme, transverse muscles from myotomes of the mesoderm, and heart muscle from the myoepicardial plate formed from the splanchnotome.

Smooth muscle tissue is also called visceral muscle, depending on where it meets in the body. This tissue is found in the walls of blood vessels and internal organs. The structural element of smooth muscle is a myocyte with a spindle-shaped shape (Fig. 1). The length of the cell is 20-500 μm , with a cross-section not exceeding 10 μm . The rod-like nucleus is located in the expanded middle part of the cell, and chromatin in the form of 1-2 nuclei and small granules is visible. Mitochondria and plate-like complexes are gathered around the poles of the nucleus.

Figure 1. histological structure of smooth muscle tissue.

In the cytoplasm, there are many myofilaments located along the length of the cell, which gives the cytoplasm a linearity. They have a smooth contour and do not have any signs of transverse linearity. The phrase "smooth muscle" is used accordingly. Myosin (thickness 17 nm), actin (7 nm) and intermediate (10 nm) myofilaments are distinguished. Myofilaments do not aggregate into real myofibrils in a smooth muscle cell. Amitotic division of myocytes is more common, as well as their mitotic pathway. There is also information about division by li.

Transverse muscle tissue. The structural unit of striated muscle tissue is the muscle fiber (Fig. 2), which has a transverse linearity that can be seen even with the help of a small objective of a microscope.

Fig. 2. Histological structure of transverse muscle tissue.

Muscle fibers are symplastic in structure. The diameter of the fiber is up to 100 μm , and the length can reach 12.5 cm. The shape of myosymplast is similar to a cylinder with a rounded tip.

It is a collection of many cells with a special, complex structure, which are united to perform a common task. The fiber has a shell - sarcolemma (sarcos - meat, muscle), cytoplasm (sarcoplasm), organelles and many cores. Also, the sarcoplasm stores the contractile filaments that aggregate into myofibrils.

When the sarcolemma is examined using an electron microscope, it is seen that it consists of two layers, and there is a space between the layers with a width of 14-24 nm. The inner sheet is the

plasmolemma of the myosymplast, and the outer sheet is the basement membrane. Here, too, argyrophilic fibers are attached to the basal membrane. The main feature of the inner sheet of the sarcolemma is the ability to distribute the impulse to the entire fiber. This sheet crosses the fiber in the form of T-tubes (transverse) and attaches to the plasmolemma of the opposite side. The spacing of adjacent T-tubes is equal to each other. Such a system of tubes is distributed throughout the sarcoplasm and ensures rapid propagation of the impulse throughout the fiber. The ends of the muscle fibers go to the tendons. In these places, the fiber forms finger-like bumps that penetrate into the tendon. Connective tissue fibers (argyrophilic fibrils) attached to the sarcolemma surrounding the muscle fiber contribute to a strong connection with the tendon. The thin layers of soft connective tissue surrounding the muscle fibers are called endomysium. Its fibers attach to the sarcolemma. The bundles (bundles) of muscle fibers are surrounded by a perimysium of the same tissue. The connective tissue that wraps the whole muscle from the outside is called epimysium. Blood and lymph vessels and capillaries enter the muscle through this connective tissue. Afferent (sensing) and efferent (motor) nerve fibers go to the muscle fibers. In the cytoplasm, there are many myofilaments located along the length of the cell, which gives the cytoplasm a linearity. They have a smooth contour and do not have any signs of transverse linearity. The phrase "smooth muscle" is used accordingly. Myosin (thickness 17 nm), actin (7 nm) and intermediate (10 nm) myofilaments are distinguished. Myofilaments do not aggregate into real myofibrils in a smooth muscle cell. Amitotic division of myocytes is more common, as well as their mitotic path. There is also information about how it can be divided by li.

Cross-striated muscle tissue. The structural unit of the transverse-striated muscle tissue is the muscle fiber (Fig. 2), which is also visible with the help of small lenses of the microscope. has linearity. Muscle fibers are symplastic in structure. The diameter of the fiber is up to 100 μm , and the length can reach 12.5 cm. The shape of myosymplast is similar to a cylinder with a rounded tip. It is a collection of many cells with a special, complex structure united to perform a common task. The fiber has a shell - sarcolemma (sarcos - meat, muscle), cytoplasm (sarcoplasm), organelles and many cores. Also, the sarcoplasm stores the contractile filaments that aggregate into myofibrils.

When the sarcolemma is examined using an electron microscope, it is seen that it consists of two layers, and there is a space between the layers with a width of 14-24 nm. The inner sheet is the plasmolemma of the myosymplast, and the outer sheet is the basement membrane. Here, too, argyrophilic fibers are attached to the basal membrane. The main feature of the inner sheet of the sarcolemma is the ability to spread the impulse throughout the fiber. This sheet crosses the fiber in the form of T-tubes (transverse) and attaches to the plasmolemma of the opposite side. The spacing of adjacent T-tubes is equal to each other. Such a system of tubes is spread over the entire sarcoplasm and ensures rapid propagation of the excitation throughout the fiber. The ends of the muscle fibers go to the tendons. In these places, the fiber forms finger-like bumps that penetrate into the tendon. Connective tissue fibers (argyrophilic fibrils) attached to the sarcolemma surrounding the muscle fiber contribute to a strong connection with the tendon. The thin layers of soft connective tissue surrounding the muscle fibers are called endomysium. Its fibers attach to the sarcolemma. The bundles (bundles) of muscle fibers are surrounded by a perimysium of the same tissue. The connective tissue that surrounds the whole muscle from the outside is called epimysium. Blood and lymph vessels and capillaries enter the muscle through this connective tissue. Afferent (sensing) and efferent (motor) nerve fibers go to the muscle fibers.

Historical raw material of the quadriceps muscle of the sheep protein content at the 3- and 18-month stages of postnatal ontogenesis acceleration compared to other ages, i.e. adequate and inadequate respectively, in 3 days - $78.16 \pm 0.94\%$; $76.56 \pm 0.5\%$ if there is, in 3 months - $80.42 \pm 0.9\%$; $79.83 \pm 0.98\%$, at 18 months - $84.29 \pm 0.89\%$; It was noted that it reached $479.4 \pm 6.72 \mu\text{m}^2$

The conclusion. The histomorphological structure of the muscle tissue system was studied on the basis of literature analysis. Muscle tissue consists of cells specialized for contraction. Muscle tissue is divided into three types according to its structure and function:

Skeletal muscle cells - linear, voluntary control.

Cardiac muscle cells - linear, involuntary control.

Smooth muscle cells - unstriated, are divided into muscles that have voluntary control.

Skeletal and cardiac muscle cells are called striated because they show alternating rows of striations.

In all types of muscle tissue, contraction occurs as a result of the movement of myosin enzymes along actin enzymes.

REFERENCES list

1. Shodiyev N.Sh., Dilmurodov N.B. «Sitologiya, gistologiya va embriologiya» Darslik, Toshkent 2015.
2. Ibrohimov Sh.l. va b. "Sitologiya, gistologiya va embriologiya", darslik, T. 2006.
3. Shodiyev N.Sh va b. "Sitologiya, gistologiya va embriologiya", o'quv qo'llanma, T.2006
4. Козлов Н.А “Общая гистология. Ткани домашних млекопитающих животных.” Учебн пособие для вузов СПб: Лан 2004
5. Jo Ann Eurell, Dvm, Phd., Brian L. Frappier, Dvm, Phd “Dellmann’s Textbook of Veterinary Histology” Australia ©2006 Blackwell Publishing.
6. Allamurodov M.X. va Dilmurodov N.B. «Hayvonlar anatomiyasi» fanidan amaliy mashg'ulotlar bo'yicha uslubiy qo'llanma. Samarqand 2005
7. Юдичев Ю.Ф. ва бошқалар «Анатомия домашних животных», Омск 2003
8. Антипова Л.В. и др. “Анатомия и гистология сельскохозяйственных животных.” Уч.пос.Москва. Колос.
9. Dilmurodov, N. (2010). The Developmental Peculiarities of Tubular Bones of Autopodies of Sheep at Postnatal Ontogenesis in Dependence on Habitat Conditions. 新疆农业大学学报, 6.
10. Yunusov, N. B., Dilmurodov, N. B., Kuliev, B. A., & Akhmedov, S. M. (2021). The Role Of Coccal Microflora In The Etiology And Pathogenesis Of Respiratory Diseases In Lambs Of The Karakul Breed Of Uzbekistan. Int. J. of Aquatic Science, 12(3), 1923-1928.
11. Яромлович, В. А., Юнусов, Х. Б., Федотов, Д. Н., Даминов, А. С., Дилмуродов, Н. Б., & Кулиев, Б. А. (2020). Морфофункциональная характеристика вымени у коров различной продуктивности.
12. Bakhodirovich, Y. J., & Bobokulovich, D. N. (2022). Treatment and Prevention of Transmissive Veneric Sarcoma in Dogs. Eurasian Medical Research Periodical, 7, 81-85.
13. Дилмуродов, Н. Б., Дониёров, Ш. З., & Чориев, О. Н. (2022). Бройлер жўжалар елка суяги таркибидаги кул ва умумий органик моддалар микдорини постнатал онтогенезда ўзгариши. Вестник Ветеринарии и Животноводства, 2(1).
14. Mukhtarov, E. A., Bobokulovich, D. N., & Ishkuvvatovich, B. E. (2022). Dynamics of some indicators of sheep blood. Journal of new century innovations, 17(2), 36-42.
15. Abdig'ulomovich, M. E., & Babaqulovich, D. N. (2022, April). Dynamics of triglitsrin in blood in different conditions. In E Conference Zone (pp. 202-204).
16. Дилмуродов, Н., & Мухторов, Э. (2021). Турли яшаш шароитидаги хисори зотли қўйлар постнатал онтогенезида оёқлар проксимал мускуларининг морфометрик хусусиятлари. Вестник Ветеринарии и Животноводства, 1(1).
17. Mukhtarov, B. Z., & Dilmurodov, N. B. (2021). Pathomorphological changes in poultry pododermatitis in cows. Academicia: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(4), 1679-1683.

18. Muxtarov, E. A., Normuradova, Z. F., & Dilmurodov, N. B. (2022). Qo'ylar muskullarning morfometrik o'zgarish dinamikasi. *Agrobiotexnologiya va veterinariya tibbiyoti ilmiy jurnali*, 407-410.
19. ДИЛМУРОДОВ, Н. Б. (2015). Физические параметры метаподия овец гиссарской породы в постнатальном онтогенезе. *Вестник ветеринарии*, (4), 58-60.
20. Mukhtarov, B. Z., & Dilmurodov, N. B. Some Biochemical Indicators of Blood in Prosperous Cows in Pure Pododermatitis. *JournalNX*, 6(06), 58-62.
21. Дилмуродов, Н. Б., Дониёров, Ш. З., & Султонов, Б. А. (2021). Бройлер жўжалари узангилик (цевка) суягининг морфогенезига пробиотиклар таъсири. *Вестник Ветеринарии и Животноводства*, 1(2).
22. Muzafar, Y., Zoyir, M., & Nasriddin, D. (2023). Morphometric features of the femor bone of different rabbits. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(9), 563-570.
23. Zafarovich, D. S., Babakulovich, D. N., & Norboyevich, C. O. (2022). Changes in the Amount of Calcium and Phosphorus in the Composition of the Femur Bone of Broiler Chickens in Postnatal Ontogenesis. *International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology*, 2(2), 21-25.
24. Dilmurodov, N., Mirzoyev, Z., & Normuradova, Z. (2022). Морфогенез бедренной кости кроликов породы фландер на разных физиологических стадиях. *Вестник ветеринарии и животноводства (ssuv. uz)*, 2(2).
25. Мухторов, Э., & Дилмуродов, Н. (2021). Ҳисори зотли кўйлар елканинг сонинг тўрт бошли мускули толасининг ядроси диаметрини постнатал онтогенезда ўзгариши. In *International Conference on Agriculture Sciences, Environment, Urban and Rural Development*. (pp. 49-52).
26. Dilmurodov, N. B., Yakhshieva, S. K., & Rakhmanova, G. S. (2021). Probiotics influence on the glandular stomach of broiler chickens in postnatal morphogenesis. *Academicia: an international multidisciplinary research journal*, 11(2), 1656-1660.
27. Dilmurodov, N., Rakhmanova, G., Fedotov, D., & Normuradova, Z. (2022). Возрастная морфология надпочечников у птиц. *Вестник ветеринарии и животноводства (ssuv. uz)*, 2(2).
28. Po'lat, Z., & Nasriddin, D. (2022). Tovuqlar ovqat hazm organlarining tuzilishidagi morfofunktsional xususiyatlar (Adabiyot ma'lumotlari tahlili). *Conferencea*, 120-125.
29. Qurbonova, N., & Dilmurodov, N. (2022). Problems in learning a foreign language. *Ilm fan taraqqiyotida zamonaviy metodlarning qo'llanilishi*, 2(28), 51-53.
30. Дониёров, Ш. З., & Дилмуродов, Н. Б. (2021). Бройлер жўжалар елка суяги таркибидаги намлик миқдорини постнатал онтогенезда ўзгариш динамикаси. In *International Conference on Agriculture Sciences, Environment, Urban and Rural Development*. (pp. 45-48).
31. Shuxratovna, R. G., Babakulovich, D. N., Fayzullayevna, N. Z., & Nikolayevich, F. D. (2022). "Tuxum yo 'nalishidagi tovuqlar reproduktiv organlarining postnatal morfogenezi"(adabiyot ma'lumotlari asosida). *Scientific Impulse*, 1(4), 603-608.
32. Tursagatov, J. M., & Dilmurodov, N. B. (2022). Har xil yoshli qorako'l qo'ylar stilopodiy suyaklari diafizi qalinligining o'zgarish dinamikasi. *Agrobiotexnologiya va veterinariya tibbiyoti ilmiy jurnali*, 949-953.
33. Dilmurodov, N., & Doniyorov, S. (2021). Влияние пробиотиков на морфогенез костей цевка у циплят-бройлеров. *Вестник ветеринарии и животноводства (ssuv. uz)*, 1(2).
34. Tursagatov, J. M., & Dilmurodov, N. B. (2023). Influence of the Conditions Regions on the Linear Parameters Forearm-Elbow Bones of Karakul Sheep. *European Journal of Veterinary Medicine*, 3(6), 8-11.

35. Ulomovich, m. E. A., & Babakulovich, D. N. Morphogenesis Of The Hind Leg Distal Muscles Of Hissar Sheep Of Different Breeds In Different Ecological Conditions. *JournalNX*, 6(06), 25-29.
36. Дилмуродов, Н. Б., & Мухтаров, Э. А. (2021). Ҳисори зотли қўйлар постнатал онтогенезида соннинг икки бошли мускулларнинг морфологик хусусиятлари. *Veterinariya meditsinasi Agrozoovetsersvs.*
37. Нурмухамедов, Б. М., Дилмуродов, Н. Б., Эшбуриев, С. Б., & Рахмонов, У. А. (2019). Морфофункциональная характеристика яичников у коз.
38. Дилмуродов, Н. Б., & Мухтаров, Э. А. (2020). Ҳисори зотли қўйлар олдинги оёқ дистал мускулларнинг постнатал онтогенезидаги морфологик хусусиятлари. *Veterinariya meditsinasi.*
39. Yakubov, M. A., Dilmurodov, N. B., Muxtorov, B. Z., & Muxtarov, E. A. (2023). Change of biochemical indicators of blood in putural pododermatitis of productive cows. *Scientific impulse*, 1(9), 555-562.
40. Мухтаров, Э. А., & Дилмуродов, Н. (2021). Ҳисори зотли қўйлар постнатал онтогенезида мускулларнинг айрим кимёвий кўрсаткичлари. *Veterinariya meditsinasi Agrozoovetsersvs.*
41. Мухторов, Э. А., & Дилмуродов, Н. Б. (2020). Ҳисори зотли қўйлар постнатал онтогенезида оёқ мускулларининг морфологик кўрсаткичларига яшаш шароитини таъсири. *журнал агро процессинг*, 2(2).
42. Дилмуродов, Н. Б., Пардаева, Ш. А., & Мирзаев, С. М. (2023). Сигирларда пододерматит жараёнларини келтириб чиқарувчи омиллар ва кечиш хусусиятлари. *Вестник ветеринарии и животноводства*, 3(1).
43. Рахманова, Г. Ш., Дилмуродов, Н. Б., & Федотов, Д. Н. (2022). Гистологическое состояние надпочечников у кур в условиях птицефабрик узбекистана. *Agrobiotexnologiya va veterinariya tibbiyoti ilmiy jurnali*, 353-355.
44. Zafarovich, D. S., & Babakulovich, D. N. (2021). Changes In Natural And Hygroscopic Moisture Content Of Broiler Chickens In Postnatal Ontogenesis. *nveo-natural volatiles & essential oils journal| NVEO*, 15710-15713.
45. Федотов, Д. Н., & Дилмуродов, Н. Б. (2020). Практическое изучение микропрепаратов в общей и частной гистологии.
46. Нурмухамедов, Б. М., Дилмуродов, Н. Б., Эшбуриев, С. Б., & Эшматов, Г. Х. (2019). Морфофункциональные изменения в яичниках коз под влиянием гонадотропных препаратов.
47. Zarpullayev, P., & Dilmurodov, N. (2022). *Ferula assafoetida* o 'simligining hayvonlarning reproduktiv faoliyatiga TA'SIRI. *Conferencea*, 88-90.
48. Abdigulomovich, M. E., & Bobokulovich, D. N. (2021). Changes In The Postnatal Ontogenesis Of Historological Indicators Of The Four-Headed Muscle Number Of Hissari Sheep. *nveo-natural volatiles & essential oils journal| nveo*, 15705-15709.
49. Дилмуродов, Н. Б. (2009). Влияние экологических условий на онтогенез кости метаподий у овец. *Ветеринария*, (4), 42-43.
50. Дилмуродов, Н., & Худойназарова, Н. (2019). Закономерности изменения суставного и метаэпифизарного хряща костей акроподий в постнатальном онтогенезе.
51. Dilmurodov, N. B., Karimov, M. G., & Normurodova, Z. F. (2018). Hayvonlar marfologiyasi fanidan amaliy laboratoriya mashg'ulotlari.

52. Dilmurodov, N. B., Yakhshieva, S. K., & Rakhmanova, G. S. Probiotics influence on the glandular stomach of broiler chickens in postnatal morphogenesis, *cademia: an international multidisciplinary research journal*.
53. Mukhtarov, E. A. U., & Dilmurodov, N. B. Morphogenesis of the hind leg distal muscles of hissar sheep of different breeds in different ecological conditions. *A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal*. P, 25-29.
54. Dilmurodov, N., & Mukhtorov, E. Effect of ecological conditions on the morphometric properties of wrist joint muscles in postnatal ontogenesis of sheep.
55. Турсагатов, Ж. М., & Дилмуродов, Н. Б. (2022). Ҳар хил ёшли қорақўл қўйлар стилоподий суяклари диафизи калинлигининг ўзгариш динамикаси. *Agrobiotexnologiya va veterinariya tibbiyoti ilmiy jurnali*, 949-953.
56. Muxtarov, E. (2021). Changes In The Postnatal Ontogenesis Of Histological Indicators Of The Four-Headed Muscle Number Of Hisori Sheep. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
57. Дилмуродов, Н. (2016). Суяк илиги бўшлиғини қўйларнинг ёши ва зотига кўра ўзгариши. *Зооветеринария*, 2, 19-21.
58. Zafarovich, D. S., Babakulovich, D. N., Khojimukhammad, K., Suhrob, A., & Bunyodjon, R. (2023). Change of ash and total organic substances of the humerus chicken broiler applied probiotics during postnatal ontogenesis. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(12), 399-406.
59. Zafarovich, D. S., Babakulovich, D. N., Kakhramon, N., & Otabek, Y. (2023). Postnatal ontogenesis of macroatomical indicators of tarsometatarsus of broiler chickens receiving probiotics. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(12), 345-350.
60. NB Dilmurodov,. Change of the morphometric dimensions of the sheep's local ring and thyroid areas during postnatal ontogenesis. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*. 2023/12/9.
61. Dilmurodov, Nasriddin Bobokulovich; Mukhtarov, Elmurod Abdihulomovich; Urinboyev, Hasanboy Abdusamad o'g'li. The dynamics of changing of the sheep glossary muscle. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*. 2023/12/6.
62. Mukhtorov, Elmurod Abdigulomovich; Dilmurodov, Nasriddin Bobokulovich; Azimoba, Dilnura Madat qizi. (2023). Postnatal morphogenesis of histological indicators of the quadrice muscle of hisori breed sheep. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(12), 240–247.
63. N.B. Dilmurodov. (2023). Characteristics of changes in the postnatal ontogenesis of the scapula of small corn molars. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(12), 195–203.
64. S.X. Yakhshieva, N.B. Dilmurodov,. (2023). Intestinal morphogenesis in postnatal ontogenesis of broiler chicks. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(12), 232–239.
65. N.B. Dilmurodov, (2023). Characteristics of changes in postnatal ontogenesis of the pelvic bone of small corn molars. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
66. Avazbek, B., Javohir, M., & Elmurod, M. (2022). Qondagi albuminning turli shashroitlardagi ko'rsatkichlari. *World scientific research journal*, 2(2), 128-132.
67. Oybek, A., & Elmurod, M. (2022). Morphometric changes of skeletal muscles of animals in the postnatal period (review of literature). *Conferencea*, 161-165.
68. Кулиев, Б. А., Ахмедов, С. М., & Мухтаров, Э. А. (2022). Лечение т-активином ягнят каракульской породы, больных пневмонией. *Journal of new century innovations*, 17(4), 130-138.

69. Alimjonovich, Y. M., & Abdiglomovich, M. E. (2022). Estropane some morphogenesis of cow blood. *American Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 6, 38-42.
70. Кулиев, Б. А., Ахмедов, С. М., & Мухтаров, Э. А. (2022). Патоморфология пневмоний у ягнят каракульской породы. *Journal of new century innovations*, 17(4), 146-154.
71. Мухторов, Э. А. (2020). Действие условия содержания на морфологические показатели мускулатуры конечности постнатального онтогенеза у гиссарской породы овец. *В современном состоянии, традиции и инновационные технологии в развитии апк* (pp. 137-140).
72. Мухторов, Э. А. (2019). Ҳисори зотли қўйлар орқа оёқ мускулларининг постнатал онтогенездаги морфометрик хусусиятлари. *журнал агро процессинг*, (4).
73. Alimjonovich, Y. M., Rajabovich, M. Z., & Abdiglomovich, M. E. (2022). Morphometric characteristics of tibi bone in postnatal ontogenesis of rabbits of different breeds. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 9, 324-330.
74. Бобоназаров, Э. И., & Мухтаров, Э. А. (2022). Применение препарата полиамидин-п для профилактики и лечение пироплазмоза крупного рогатого скота. *Journal of new century innovations*, 17(2), 43-50.
75. Мухтаров, Э. А. (2020). Қўйлар постнатал онтогенезида мускулларнинг айрим кимёвий хусусиятлари.
76. Muxtarov, E. (2022). Estropane some morphogenesis of cow blood. *American Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences*.
77. Karim o'g'li, R. K., Ikram o'g'li, E. U., & Abdigulomovich, M. E. (2023). Karakol sheep lymphatic flow from the skin of the distal and wrax of the front leg. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
78. Umarjon, E., Khujakhan, R., & Elmurod, M. (2023). Liver histomorphological structure. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(12), 213-220.